

INNOVATION IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article focuses on the role and importance of innovation in education. That is, what innovations to use in education, about their effectiveness. There is also talk about the types of educational innovations, their role in higher education.

Key words: Innovation, Education, Educational innovations, pedagogical innovation, scientific and methodological innovation, technological innovation.

Introduction: The world has changed under the influence of innovation. Innovation can be defined as new inventions or new ideas, new ideas and approaches. (March 2016) In some societies, new ways of doing things like educating people are seen as very valuable, while others feel they don't support the idea. However, the world has not stopped emerging people with new approaches to the world who are creating a prolific and effective environment in all spheres. It has been said that the role of innovation has been noticeable by the sight of impressive consequences in terms of education.

It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts "educational innovations" and "innovations in education". Innovation in education is a broader concept than educational innovation. They include educational, scientific and technological, infrastructural, economic, social, legal, administrative and other innovations.

Educational innovations are understood as a procedure or method of educational activity that differs significantly from established practice and is used to increase the level of efficiency in a competitive environment. Educational innovations include pedagogical innovation, scientific and methodological innovation, educational and technological innovation.

Pedagogical innovation. Pedagogical innovation is a process that reinvents teaching practices, with the goal of better supporting student learning.

Scientific innovation. Scientific innovation involves the successful exploitation of new ideas to generate new techniques, products and processes. Traditionally, scientific innovation has been viewed as a process starting with curiosity-driven, basic research which generates new understanding.

The Methods Innovation (MI) research group focuses on supporting and improving the understanding and application of contemporary methods in the study of the social world.

A technological innovation is a new or improved product or process whose technical characteristics are significantly different from previous ones. Implemented technological product innovations are new products that have been put on the market (product innovations) or processes in applications (process innovations).

It is substantiated that the education market is one of the most important elements of the national innovation system. Higher education institutions that have chosen an innovation-based development, become competitive leaders on the education market. The formation of forms of education and the use of perfect controlling mechanisms at each educational institution will give the opportunity to create single educational space, which is able to meet the needs of society in quality education with specific opportunities of customers in the educational market. The main components of the innovation development of higher education institutions are determined.

Many scholars proved that innovation in education depicted generally has resulted in innovative developments. They are illustrated by development in educational process, staff development, social development, technical and technological development, development of international cooperation, economic development and organization development. Among these innovative developments, all of them can have influential impacts on society. Namely, economic development preserves more contribution to the development of all spheres and plays a key role to the development of a certain country.

According to Mykhailyshyn et al. (2018), there are three types of innovation in the internal environment of education which are the educational innovation, administrative or managerial innovation, and ideological innovation.

The main factors of innovation in internal environment of universities include

- educational innovations: the content of the curriculum, new teaching technologies, high professionalism of teaching staff, organizational and methodological support of educational process
- administrative (managerial) innovation: support for innovative university structure, general management system and its properties, management system at the

level of structural subdivisions (faculties, departments), system of provision with educational services quality.

- ideological innovation : university participating in the programs , competitions and other events held with the participation of government institution and Ministry of Education Ukraine,

- availability of state order for specialist training from line ministries, the presence of mechanisms of interaction between universities and the labor market.

Educational innovations. Educational innovations are the essence of innovative education Innovation in education is a broader concept than educational innovation. They include educational, scientific atechnological ,infrastructural,economic, social, legal, administrative and other innovations Scientific and technological innovations are the result of research and development in the shape of intellectual property and are transferred for implementation and application in production Scientists consider its purpose in creating an optimal and sustainable educational and organizational, scientific and methodological and regulatory and administrative environment that provides support of innovative approaches to the educational process, which are focused on the integration of scientific and educational potential of universities and science and partnerships with employers. sectorial Such understanding of innovative development enables institutions to implement new approaches to the choice of strategic objectives, based not only on their own interests, but first of all the interests of consumers of innovative education system products: society, state, employees, students and others.

Conclusion. Taking all the points into consideration, I would once more put emphasis on innovation in education. Most importantly, the outcomes that have been generated by innovation in the field of education are worth stating more and more. I hold a firm belief that people of every society should be open to the forthcoming shifts. In most cases people can be open to innovative ideas and accept them if only they bring them better

REFERENCES:

1. March, T. (2016). starting an education revolution: the role of innovation. education technologysolution.com. 1. Halyna Mykhayshyn, Oksana
2. Kondur, Lesia Serman (2018) Innovation of education and educational innovations in conditions of modern education institutions Andrushchenko V.P. Priorities of the education development of XXI century. Current philosophical andculturological problems of the present.
3. Journal of Educational Research and Indigenous Studies Volume: 2 (1), 2020 Journal website: www.jerisjournal.com e - ISSN 2682-759X